

Have the Men Had Enough? : A Portrayal of Domestic Inequality

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Abstract:

*Margaret Forster, the most prolific and critically acclaimed writer, engaged herself in creative writing since 1964. She has devoted her attention to depict a family and domestic issues. She makes her protagonists to move within a family circle with duties and responsibilities. A family is the prime institute which crushes women's individual identity and they get entrapped in familial obligations. Margaret Forster's novel *Have the Men Had Enough?* effectively throws light on how women are overburdened within a domestic sphere and how men are set free. The present paper attempts to draw the attention towards the fact that how patriarchal ideology and psyche controls a private sphere. It also aims to point out how the different generations react on familial issues.*

Keywords: *Familial Life, Gender Roles, Domestic Inequality.*

Introduction:

Margaret Forster (1938-2016) has explored the rich and fertile territory of family relationships, the tyranny of love and obligation that has confined women in a family for generations together. It is obvious that the subject matter of her novel is the family life of the contemporary working and lower middle-class women and the daily issues which they confront them. One can experience Forster's skill in depicting conflict that appears in human relationships and her ability in uncovering the chaotic domestic lives of women. The lives of women, the obligations that families impose on women, and the pressures of domestic servitude that women have suffered over the centuries both in paid service and as wives and mothers, are at the centre of much of Forster's writing.

Forster places her characters within a circle of family and thoroughly examines their lives. She makes her protagonist to move within a family circle with duties and responsibilities. Through her fictional work, Forster raises her

voice against traditional feminists' attitude, approach and treatment as it has stuck up with the issues of equality and wider opportunities for women. Traditional feminists' approach ponders over the women's issues on a large scale of society, they measure women's status in a patriarchal ideology, their struggle for women's identity on the vast canvas of society but Forster looks beyond it and expects the individual identity of women within a small world i.e. a family. Forster remains loyal to her urge to expose the crushing of individual's identity in a private sphere. Women are trapped in various roles in a family and thus they are recognized by their roles and not as a separate personality. The roles attributed to them become their identity. Moreover, their roles within a family change like a moving circle and while maintaining and handling relations, she has no chance to show her real identity. According to Forster a family is the major factor which crushes woman's identity. In her portrait of family, a woman has to bear the burden of many responsibilities and duties. She

becomes one with the family relations, struggles, shapes and adjusts herself according to the demand of the situation but it is at the cost of her identity. Forster's concern for the loosing identity of a woman in the family is the main theme of her novels. Her female protagonists are caught up in duties, obligations and responsibilities. In a true sense, Forster presents reality of the life of women. Woman is the main pillar of the family but her identity, strength and power are lost. Forster's novels are notable because they raise the fact that apart from their social status, women are marginalized in a family. Forster protests against whatever happens to women within a family circle. Through her work she puts forth a basic question about women's identity in a family. Traditional feminism definitely fights for women's status, their issues, their rights etc. but they are discussed from patriarchal point of view only. It seems that feminism has not paid much attention to the domestic problems of women whereas Forster desperately tries to raise her voice to promote the plight of women within a family.

Have the Men Had Enough?

Have the Men Had Enough? (1989) is an outcome of Forster's troublesome domestic life which she underwent. Forster's mother-in-law Marion Davis had dementia. She was the eye-witness of her declining conditions. In one of the interviews Forster expresses her experience of handling her mother-in-law as follows:

It's degrading, it's degrading for the person dying and it's degrading

for the people watching the dying. There is no-you just feel disgusted

and helpless and you feel such pity, they're just lumps, just things. And

however much you love them you want to put them out of this misery,

not just your own misery, but their misery I think (Forster 5).

Forster wrote this novel after the death of her mother-in-law. She wove the story of disease and its consequences on family members. The novel is produced, 'out of rage and pity' (Jones 27). Forster has become successful in creating such an atmosphere that it raises rage and pity among readers. Like characters, readers also experience rage and pity. Forster brilliantly presents a portrait of the family wrapped in the problem of Grandma. The problem has become such a burden that they are unable to think of anything else.

Have The Men Had Enough? has an autobiographical touch. It presents a story of three women belonging the same family but representing three different generations with their different attitudes towards the old age and its problems. The female characters are: Grandma, daughter-in-law and granddaughter while male characters are Charlie and Stuart. The core of the novel is how Grandma and her problem is treated from the different perspectives of men and women within a family. It tells a story about a Grandma who had always been a caretaker of a family and now is unable to take care of herself. *Have the Men Had Enough?* is a realistic story that deals with a family coping with their mother's loss of mental ability to memorize i.e. dementia. As a result of it, she loses her sense of identity and time that leads to very painful life.

As the narrative progresses, it becomes clear that Grandma is unable to take care of herself which creates sympathy among the readers. The novel also brings into light how women are over-burdened in familial duties and responsibilities while men are set free from all the burdens. It also depicts instances of various pangs of stresses like physical, emotional, economic and psychological on members of a family especially, while dealing with elderly person. The novel

depicts three women closely connected to Grandma. They are Bridget, Jenny and Hannah who are the daughter, daughter-in-law and granddaughter respectively. At the same time, it also narrates men's attitude and treatment on the background of the novel. When things go beyond the control for women to handle Grandma, the decision comes forward that Grandma should send to "home.". However, this option is looked differently from everyone. For instance, Bridget stands opposite to it. Bridget, unlike her brothers is aware of mother's sacrifice to bring them up. The strong and loveable tie of the relationship binds them together as their relationship is based on unconditional love and lot of concern for each other. These things are reflected in the thought of Bridget who opposes to send Grandma to Home. Even she is ready to lose her job for Grandma. Forster has discharged the thought of Bridget:

She will give up her job, a job which is no ordinary job, one to which she has given her life and from which she derives great satisfaction, and she will wait on her mother who cannot walk or talk and may take years to die (The Men 231).

When Jenny allows Charlie to send Grandma to 'Home', a sense of guilt develops in Jenny that she cannot avoid. She thinks:

I felt I had abandoned her brutally and could not live with this for a whole week. . . if I found her unhappy, I would certainly bring her home without any permission from him (The Men 182).

On the other hand, Hannah the third generation of women in Forster's novels has a different approach than the earlier generations. Women from third generations show different opinions and they do not bother with what is going on in the family. Hannah is a representative of third generation who has objective approach

towards domestic problems. For Hannah, Bridget is a topic of curiosity. Hannah observes Bridget's life objectively and draws a conclusion that Bridget suffers lot due to Grandma and appreciates her love, patience and tolerance towards Grandma. But Hannah is sure that she does not want to follow Bridget's life. It becomes clear that she will not devote or sacrifice her life for Jenny, though she feels sympathy for Grandma, Bridget and Jenny. Her service to Grandma is just a duty for her. Forster's third generation characters are hungry for liberalization, modernization and free relationships and they have practical attitude. Hannah's bitter comment exposes the truth of contemporary domestic life.

What am I going to do with Mum when she's old?

Why is it all such a terrible problem and fuss?

Why doesn't someone do something?

(The Men 164).

At one point in the novel, Hannah bitterly criticizes her family members for their treatment to Grandma, 'They make Grandma sound like a great big stone they are all carrying on their backs' (The Men 52). She also expresses genuine love for Grandma, 'her own love for her grandmother, unburdened by the terrible conflicting needs and responsibilities of the adults, remains constant right to the end' (The Men 85). Forster skillfully exposes emotions and feelings of women which are indications of good interpersonal relationships of women. *Have the Men Had Enough?* is the first novel of Forster which depicts good interpersonal relationships among women. Female characters in the novel are much matured and they have understanding capacity for each other's problems and needs. They extend helping hands to each other when they are totally neglected by men in the family. Even a thirteen years boy Adrian's comment speaks of mentality of male characters. Adrian says, '...it's women's work... he says he does his

bit in providing that background Male Presence (72). Charlie remarks:

. . . *so long as Grandma has any pleasure in life, he would not want to put her sleep (he does not say 'kill'). As long as the quality of Grandma's life is reasonably good, then no one has the right to end it. And he would not want to. . . (The Men 143-44).*

Have the Men Had Enough? strongly opposes male mentality that domesticity is considered as a women's work and men are supposed to be out of domestic sphere that they have nothing to do with domestic problems. Even Grandma also comments on the same thing, 'women should, women are supposed to keep the family together' (The Men 12). It means the interpersonal between men and women is not at all sound. Men have no concern for women and their problems. Stuart's attitude towards Grandma typifies male attitude, 'she has 'had her day' and should be 'packed off.' (The Men 50). This shows men including Stuart are indifferent to domestic problems.

Women in the family are engaged in taking care of Grandma. They try to understand her mentality but the men in a family remain aloof and at the distant. Men move away from their responsibility while women undergo pains while treating grandma. Forster keeps the male characters on the periphery of domestic lives of women. They are not shown wrapped in domestic problems like female characters. But they prefer to be on the border thinking that money can solve all problems. At one point in the novel, Charlie says, '. . . that we're lucky to have the money to solve our problem (The Men 103). This depiction of male characters bring forward realistic picture of women's domestic lives where they have to fight alone and bear every troublesome domestic problems.

Whatever may be the outlook of female characters- i.e. traditional or modern, they are strong, determined, and confident to battle against familial issues. They reveal supportive and unsupportive natures of parents, lovers or husbands. They also reveal the difficulties of coming in terms with a gender which their nature store and reflect while moving either in a family or a society.

Have the Men Had Enough? also underlines the tensions and worries of the relationship. Problems, worries, tensions and duties surpass love, respect, concern, sharing and bindings in the domestic lives of Forster's characters. This surpassing deteriorates a healthy family life. What Forster expects is nothing but understanding between characters and this lack of understanding shatters the interpersonal relationships of characters.

Forster depicts domestic lives of women and thus shows her keen interest in working class women's lives. She effectively focuses on domestic roles of women, their duties and responsibilities, obligations, expectations, burdens and disputes. Men and women relationship as well as women and women relationship do remain at the centre of Forster's novels. She truthfully records that women are always under the burden of familial duties and responsibilities. Forster employs contradictory characters and these characters with their peculiarities make the plot moveable. Self-sacrificed traditional and devotional women as well as liberal, modern and self-dominated women do appear in the novels of Forster. But the number of sufferer women goes high in the novel of Forster.

Forster's *Have the Men Had Enough?* draws the attention towards the fact that at the men as well as feminism have not paid required attention to the problems of women at homes. Wollstonecraft, Mill and Forster are not against

the institution of family but they are against of corrupted families. Families are corrupted because of less burdened men and over-burdened women. Feminism of course, has paid attention to it but there is more need to pay more attention. A lack of understanding, patience, endurance, acceptance of truth and ups and downs in life have made the families shattered. Women as well as men have to utilize their education, talent, sensibility and ability to have healthy families. Forster regrettably depicts unhappy pictures of women in the twenty- first century.

According to Forster roles of men and women are equally important to build healthy families. One can easily understand that Forster is inquisitive about healthy domestic life. She laments over the present situation of families and domestic lives. To restore families and domestic lives, feminism should be brought into practice from theories. She firmly believes in practical feminism which lacks in families, societies and nations. It is the duty of men and women to bring practical feminism in the society. It seems that society has misunderstood the word feminism; it is not peaceful but practical doctrine.

Conclusion:

Forster's *Have the Men Had Enough?* handles the most neglected but the most sensitive topic of domestic lives of women. By depicting

three generations and their different attitudes, she links feminism with domestic lives of women. She brilliantly exposes how women's world is deprived of support from male dominated society. If men and women do not treat equally to each other at domestic level, an institution of family will come to at the last stage of deterioration. The novelist wants to suggest that the existence of the family as an institution is in danger as family members live in broken relationships. Absence of love, practical attitudes and approaches may invite disaster for a family. The title of the novel *Have the Men Had Enough?* itself is suggestive, catchy, apt and reflecting domestic lives of women on the background of men's world in a family.

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